

ENERGY STORAGE SERVICES OPTIMIZATION IN THE CONTEXT OF A BATTERY SWAPPING BUSINESS MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Electric vehicles (EVs) hold promises to revolutionize transport decarbonization, but face challenges such as grid constraints, high costs, and long charging times. In this context, battery swapping emerges as a solution, offering scheduled charging, quick replacements, and utilizing station batteries for energy services. This study assesses the viability of supplying energy services to major consumers through battery swapping stations. It highlights the advantages of integrating charging and swapping stations to address challenges in widespread EV adoption, focusing on external charging stations. After a first assessment, which gathered some key data like hourly energy demand, electricity costs and grid fees, a detailed analysis is conducted to identify daily or seasonal trends in demand for a specific case study. In addition, an optimization procedure for the case study has been realized to minimize the annual energy cost. The results demonstrate a noteworthy reduction in peak demand, amounting to less than half of the original combined peak demand. In addition, thanks to the exploitation of the spread in the electricity costs during the day and the peak capacity reduction, annual economic savings reach more than € 80'000 in total. This underscores the efficacy of a battery swapping system not only in optimizing peak demand but also in capitalizing on cost differentials in electricity pricing, thereby contributing to considerable economic benefits.

1 INTRODUCTION

The release of greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere undeniably contributed to global warming and its actual increasing trend [1]. Fossil fuels are widely used in vehicles and the transport sector is one of the largest contributors to the global emissions, with an annual growth of 1.7% on average [2]. The electrification of the sector has emerged as the main strategy on the pursuit of decarbonization.

The adoption of electric vehicles, especially battery-powered ones (BEVs), is crucial for decarbonizing the transportation sector. These vehicles generate no emissions at the tailpipe, and their overall emissions will decrease further as the grid incorporates more renewable energy sources. A future net zero emissions scenario is only feasible with the introduction of EVs, and sales of this type of vehicles shall represent 60% of total sales by 2030 to limit the rise in global temperature to 1.5 degrees [3].

In addition to the evident advantage of reducing GHGs emissions, the incorporation of electric vehicles (EVs) into the transportation ecosystem brings forth other environmental and socio-economic benefits. These include noise reduction, decreased reliance on imported fuels, better air quality in the cities and lower overall transportation costs. Nevertheless, several constraints may impede the widespread adoption of EVs, notably the strain on the grid caused by charging [4 - 5], as well as the high initial purchase costs and extended wait times for charging.

Battery swapping, as an alternative and integration to conventional charging, can offer solutions to most of the aforementioned challenges. Battery swapping is an innovation in EV technology that enables battery electric vehicles to swiftly replace a depleted battery pack with a fully charged one, providing an alternative to recharging the vehicle at a charging station [6]. Battery swapping stations (BSS) can act as energy buffers, mitigating renewable energy curtailments [7], and reducing the stress on

distribution networks [8]. Notably, they may deliver a fully charged battery in under 5 minutes [9], effectively minimizing waiting times and addressing concerns related to range anxiety.

Another advantage of battery swapping lies in the potential utilization of the batteries situated at the swapping station for offering energy services [10]. There is extensive literature on the application of energy storage systems to provide energy services, but it is mostly limited to frequency regulation and other grid applications [11]. For example, in [12] the authors propose a strategy for sizing utility-scale energy storage systems to enhance the frequency response of transmission networks impacted by renewable energy source integration. In [13] a coordinated approach for primary frequency control in an islanded microgrid using Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Photovoltaic systems, and LED lighting loads (LEDLL) has been investigated through adjusted LEDLL luminance and BESS frequency control, the proposed method effectively reduces the size of the required battery in the low voltage network. The authors of [14] explore the use of a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) for frequency regulation in the power grid. A MATLAB/Simulink simulation model was developed to demonstrate that the BESS significantly reduces grid frequency offset by 38.1%, enhancing power response speed by at least 25 times, and maintaining high power quality. Regarding the utilization of Battery Swapping Stations (BSS) to provide energy services in [15] the authors addressed challenges in electric vehicle (EV) battery management by proposing an optimal charging-discharging schedule for battery swap stations, adapting to diverse EV characteristics. They showed that BSSs offer efficient service, support the grid through ancillary services, and introduce the innovative mobile swapping station (MSS) concept.

Energy services offered by BSS can thus be classified into three categories: i) ISO/RTO services, i.e., services provided mainly to Independent System Operators and large Transmission Network Operators, commonly known as ancillary services; ii) utility services, that are services provided to Local Transmission and Distribution Network Operators, the main goal being to defer investments to increase the capacity of the network and to relieve transport congestion at given times; (iii) customer services provided to enterprises such as commercial and industrial facilities like Time-of-Use Bill Management, Demand Charge Reduction and Increased PV self-consumption.

This work aims to contribute to have a deeper understanding on the services that can be provided by battery energy storage systems, particularly to industrial and commercial users, in the context of individual battery swapping stations with limited daily orders, by using linear programming methods with real world data for the optimization of energy storage systems.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Battery swapping model

A Battery Swapping Station (BSS) model has been developed to assess the availability of batteries in a BSS during regular daily operations. The model is based on several assumptions that align with the existing literature on the behaviour of BSSs, focusing on peak times during the day when battery swaps are more probable. It also incorporates assumptions about the allocation of daily swaps and the energy required for battery charging.

In Figure 1 it can be observed that the first swaps start after 7 AM, with a low number of orders during the morning, increasing before noon, with a peak during the following hours, decreasing afterwards until reaching another valley in the early evening hours, when it starts increasing again, with the main daily peaks occurring between 9 PM and 10 PM. Based on current practices, few or no swaps occur during the night hours, as they are either not operating or there is no demand.

Regarding the power demand, in cases where no smart charging is implemented, it follows the swapping pattern, as batteries are charged after being swapped, taking into account the needs of further swaps. The energy demand for 50 daily swaps is between 2500 kWh and 2800 kWh, with an average of around 55 kWh charged per swap considering batteries with 100 kWh storage capacity and that the battery State of Charge (SOC) ideally ranges between 20% and 80% to prolong battery lifetime.

Figure 1: Swap orders and power demand for a simulated BSS with 50 daily swaps

2.2 Model design and preliminary considerations

The operation of the BSS was simulated using a linear programming algorithm. This algorithm was used to allocate swap requests to various stored batteries while optimizing the power demand of the station. The primary objective was to compute the number of stored batteries required to meet the various daily demands or to determine the number of batteries necessary to fulfil all swap orders under a fixed contracted power capacity. The following assumptions were considered for the model:

- No swaps between 12:00 AM and 08:00 AM.
- Batteries in the BSS have a total capacity of 100 kWh, typical of a full electric SUV.
- Batteries are numbered from 1 to the total number (13 or 21) and swapped sequentially, when the last available battery is reached, the counter is restarted.
- Energy provided with each swap is on average 55 kWh ranging between 50 kWh and 60 kWh.
- Maximum battery charging power is 60 kW, so a battery can be charged and be available to swap in around 1 hour.
- A maximum of 2 swaps can be performed in a 15-minute period (8 per hour).

The model was then run multiple times with swap orders randomly assigned. This approach was used to verify the BSS's ability to meet the requirements, regardless of the specific characteristics of the order curve.

The outcomes of the model run are reported in Figure 2. Initially, the system was analysed for existing BSS configurations with 13 (blue, see Figure 2) and 21 batteries (orange, see Figure 2). The results were then compared to assess the advantage of having additional batteries to mitigate the power demand of the system. It was observed that for low daily swap volumes (below 40), the required power demands were nearly identical, indicating no benefit in having more batteries. This is due to the fact that the power management is already optimized, and maintaining a lower power demand does not allow for the charging of extra batteries during overnight hours when there's no demand. For instance, when the maximum power of the station is 60 kW, only one battery can be charged at a time, allowing a total of

8 batteries to be charged between 12:00 AM and 08:00 AM, and a total of 24 batteries can be charged on each day. Consequently, a maximum of 24 swaps can be executed when the number of batteries is 8 or more. If the number of swaps conducted is 24, any additional batteries beyond the initial 8 may remain unused or serve other purposes. This number of swaps can only be achieved if the swaps are evenly distributed during daytime, as the power allows charging 1 battery per hour, otherwise more power would be needed.

Figure 2: Daily swaps and maximum power demand for 2 configurations

However, when the daily swap count exceeds 40, an additional 45 kW capacity is required for the case of 13 batteries. Beyond 50 swaps per day, constraints arise due to limitations on swaps per hour, demanding substantial power increases or additional batteries. With daily swap exceeding 50, noticeable differences emerge, particularly as the minimum required power capacity allows for the charging of more than 13 batteries at nighttime, so more of the 21 can be used. For instance, with an installed power of 300 kW, approximately 80 swaps can be executed using a 13-battery setup, while the 21-battery configuration can achieve more than 100 swaps. In contrast, experimentation with an 8-battery configuration revealed that up to 30 daily swaps necessitate almost the same power. However, it's important to highlight that 40 daily swaps can be performed with only 8 batteries and around 150 kW capacity. Additionally, it is noteworthy that with a sufficient power capacity, a substantial number of swaps can be achieved even with a limited quantity of stored batteries. For instance, employing a 13-battery configuration with a 450-kW connection enables the execution of over 130 swaps in a single day. This implies that the redundancy or additional batteries required for swapping is less than 10% of the total circulating batteries, and significantly lower when considering that the average user typically engages in only a few swaps per month.

3 RESULTS OF A CASE STUDY: ENERGY PROVIDER / CHARGING POINT OPERATOR

The presented model has been applied to a test case that explores a scenario of a potential Charging Point Operator (CPO), located in Germany, which aims to expand its business by installing a new charging station, close to an existing BSS. This new charging station would be provided with 4 High-Power chargers, each with a peak demand of 100 kW.

Table 1: Case study scenario

Daily charging sessions	Charging points	Installed power [kW]	Peak demand [kW]	Annual energy demand [kWh]
50	4	400	360	605,000

Figure 3 reports, for the analysed case, the trend of the power demand during the day for the charging station in normal conditions of operation, with vehicles simultaneously utilising some or all of the available charging points. Low power demand occurs during the night between 1 AM and 6 AM; then the charging power requirement starts increasing in the early morning and has a morning peak after 9 AM. The daily peak demand then occurs between 12 PM and 15 PM when several simultaneous charging sessions are demanded (a maximum of 4). Power demand depends both on the number of cars charging at the same time, and the allowed maximum charging power of each car, which makes reaching 400 kW very unlikely. Additionally, the energy demand depends on the duration of the charging session, which is usually in the order of 15 minutes due to the high power of the chargers.

Figure 3: Average daily demand for the charging station

The electricity cost in €/MWh is also reported in the secondary y axis.

3.1 Collocation opportunities

Newly developed BSS technology can now support up to 21 battery slots, and can perform a swap in less than 5 minutes, which could require charging more than 10 batteries per hour. Consequently, these installations can be equipped with a 600-kW grid connection capacity to accommodate the potential maximum power demand, even though such high-capacity levels are infrequently reached. Thus, installing a BSS together with a charging station can provide a more balanced load, improving the utilization of the available power, and reducing the required peak capacity. The BSS demand analysis has been focused on 50 swaps per day as well. While the demand curves exhibit a similar pattern, the BSS demand peaks tend to occur later in the day compared to a traditional charging station. Consequently, if the demands were to be combined, the peaks would not typically coincide.

Combining the demands (Figure 5), as if they were sharing a grid connection, the maximum simultaneous demand would be 749 kW, with a total annual energy consumption of 1.5 GWh used for charging the swapped batteries and for the high-power chargers, and total expenses (grid and energy) of € 291,000.

Figure 4: Average daily demand for a standard charging station and BSS

Figure 5: Average daily combined demand of a traditional charging station and a BSS

3.2 Load shifting option

In figure 5 it can be observed that the aggregate demand exhibits a peak in the afternoon and another peak in the evening. Nighttime experiences minimal demand, given the absence of swaps and a limited number of charging orders. This behaviour presents an opportunity to store energy overnight, therefore mitigating demand during the afternoon and evening, that are normally peak demand hours for the grid. This approach brings two benefits: a reduction in peak power demand, leading to lower grid fees, and cost savings on energy expenses due to the generally lower energy prices during nighttime. In order to quantify these advantages from an economic point of view, an analysis of the costs per installed capacity and per energy consumption needs to be carried out.

3.3 Grid fees for a reference case study

German grid and electricity costs are considered as a reference case. Grid fees in Germany are constituted by a power component (€/kW) and an energy component (€/kWh), which are applied based on the type of connection (voltage) and the utilization period (if the quotient of the total energy over the annual peak demand is under or over 2500).

$$\text{Grid fee} = (\text{peak power} * \text{power fee}) + (\text{consumed energy} * \text{energy grid fee}) \quad (1)$$

Annual utilization period is crucial since it defines the peak power fee and energy grid fee. The threshold for categorization based on the utilization period is 2500 hours. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Annual utilization period (hours)} = \text{consumed energy (kWh)} / \text{peak power (kW)} \quad (2)$$

Based on the location of the charging station, the grid connection is medium voltage, and the fees are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Grid fees

Annual usage period	< 2,500 hours		≥ 2,500 hours	
Point of delivery	Power Component [€/kW]	Energy Component [€/kWh]	Power Component [€/kW]	Energy Component [€/kWh]
High Voltage	33.43	0.0402	98.42	0.0142
High-Medium Voltage transformer	36.42	0.0550	146.44	0.0110
Medium Voltage	61.02	0.0518	104.24	0.0345
Medium - Low Voltage transformer	66.96	0.0665	146.76	0.0345
Low Voltage	68.00	0.0730	99.22	0.0606

In the case of a shared connection, the utilization period falls below 2500 hours, resulting in a lower peak power fee at 61 €/kW-year but higher energy fees at 0.0518 €/kWh. Shifting the load during peak hours to reduce peak power would extend the utilization period, leading to decreased energy fees at 0.0345 €/kWh. Despite the higher peak power fee of 104 €/kW-year, overall power expenses remain comparable as the reduction in peak power offsets the increase in the fee. This adjustment results in substantial savings that can be maximized through an optimization procedure.

3.4 Optimization

An optimization model was designed to shift the demand curve, with the goal of minimizing the total expenses incurred for both grid services and consumed energy. This involves the purchase of energy from the wholesale market, where pricing varies hourly (see Figure 4), coupled with the grid fees as mentioned earlier. The objective function to be minimized is the following:

$$O.F. = \text{Peak power [kW]} * \text{Power fee} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kW}} \right] + \sum E_{\text{demand}}(t) [\text{kWh}] * \left(E_{\text{price}}(t) \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kWh}} \right] + E_{\text{grid fee}} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kWh}} \right] \right) \quad (3)$$

The proposed objective function aims to optimize the demand curve by pushing higher demand during periods of lower energy prices, such as nighttime and noon, while reducing demand during morning and evening hours when prices are elevated. The incorporation of power fees imposes a constraint on peak demand, encouraging the pursuit of the smallest possible value. The overarching objective is to extend the utilization period, ideally resulting in a flat curve. In this scenario, the batteries would efficiently charge and discharge to align with demand fluctuations.

4 RESULTS OF THE ECONOMIC OPTIMIZATION OF THE BSS AND COMMENTS

The plot in Figure 6 illustrates the daily average curves for both the original (blue) and the shifted demand (orange). Notably, the shifted demand exhibits a partial counter-mirroring of the price curve, relocating a significant portion of the evening energy demand to the night, aligning with battery charging periods. While the curve at noon is characterized by a similar shape to the original, the peaks are effectively shaved off. It's worth mentioning that the understated changes made to the curve may not be easy to see in the averaged plot. This is because the process of averaging blurs out the finer details, making the shaved peaks less noticeable at first glance.

Figure 6: Average daily demand for the original and shifted demands

The results are summarized in Table 3, revealing a reduction in peak demand to less than half of the original combined peak demand. This decrease contributes to lower annual grid expenses. While there is a slight increase in energy demand attributed to charging losses, the strategic shift of energy consumption to periods of lower prices results in decreased energy expenses. Altogether, annual savings can amount to nearly 82'000 € in total.

Table 3: Comparison of the reference case and the optimized management

Scenario	Peak demand [kW]	Energy demand [kWh]	Energy expenses [€]	Grid expenses [€]	Total expenses [€]	Annual savings [€]
Original demand	749	1,516,000	151,000	140,000	291,000	-
Shifted demand	280	1,540,000	127,000	82,000	209,000	82,000

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present study investigates the possibility to introduce a battery swapping system in the charging stations for electric vehicles. A preliminary procedure investigates the maximum number of battery swaps and battery packs that a charging station should have, depending on the power charging capacity available.

Afterwards, a specific test case is investigated to assess: i) the peak capacity shaving possibility given by a BSS compared to a traditional charging station and ii) the optimal charging distribution during the day to exploit the electricity price spread during the day and night hours.

The results demonstrate a noteworthy reduction in peak demand, amounting to less than half of the original combined peak demand. This substantial decrease in peak demand plays a crucial role in decreasing annual grid expenses. Although there is a marginal increase in energy demand attributed to charging losses, strategically shifting energy consumption to periods of lower electricity prices results in a significant reduction in energy expenses. Taken together, the annual savings are substantial, reaching nearly € 82'000 in total. This underscores the efficacy of a battery swapping system not only in optimizing peak demand but also in capitalizing on cost differentials in electricity pricing throughout the day and night, thereby contributing to considerable economic benefits.

NOMENCLATURE

BSS	Battery Swapping Station
CPO	Charging Point Operator
GHGs	Greenhouse Gases
SOC	State of Charge

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